

Research

Dengue virus serotype 2 and 3 causing high morbidity and mortality in Swat, Pakistan

Amjad Ali ^{1,2}, Zeeshan Nasim ¹, Rafi Ur Rehman ¹, Farzana ¹, Sajid Ali ³, Fazli Zahir ¹, Aqib Iqbal ¹, Ijaz Ali ^{1,4*}, Abdul Waheed Khan ¹

¹ Institute of Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, Peshawar.

² Hazara University, Mansehra, Dhodial.

³ University of Peshawar.

⁴ Department of Biological Sciences, The University of Tulsa, Oklahoma.

* Corresponding author, Email: ijazcas@gmail.com

Abstract

Dengue, an alarmingly growing epidemic viral disease is a major health concern. Pakistan suffered several mini and major outbreaks of dengue over the past couple of years with high morbidity rates than those commonly reported from dengue epidemics globally. Hundreds of people died in the string of dengue epidemics in Pakistan since 2005. In July 2013, a major outbreak of dengue started in Swat district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) which has so far caused 57 deaths and thousands of morbidities. In this study, we screened 414 clinically diagnosed dengue patients for dengue specific antibodies, out of which 366 were found to be serologically positive by the Standard Diagnostics (SD) Dengue Duo test. All dengue virus (DENV) positive samples were then analyzed using a DENV serotype-specific reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction to identify the DENV serotypes present and to figure out active infections. In this study, 28.69% (105/366) of the serologically positive patients had active infection and DENV type 3 (DENV-3) was the most abundant serotype followed by DENV-2; similar to the outbreak in Punjab during 2010-11. The mortality rate from this epidemic to date has however been lower compared to the previous major DENV outbreak of 2010-11 in Lahore.

Keywords

Dengue outbreak, Swat, serotyping, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Abbreviations

DENV: Dengue virus, DHF: Dengue hemorrhagic fever, DSS: Dengue shock syndrome

Highlights

- 1 .Dengue outbreak in Swat, Pakistan caused heavy death toll since July 2013.
- 2 .DENV-2 and DENV-3 are the sole causative agents of high morbidity and mortality in Swat.
- 3 .Mortality rate of the dengue outbreaks in Pakistan is comparatively higher.
- 4 .Mortalities may have even occurred during primary DENV infections.

Introduction

Dengue, a major health concern of tropical and subtropical regions, is the most prevalent mosquito borne viral disease of the world [1]. The virus is transmitted by mosquito *Aedes aegypti*, which is its primary vector, but it can also be transmitted by *Aedes albopictus* [2]. In the last 50 years, dengue virus (DENV) infections have increased by 30-fold due to their spread into other countries and from urban to rural areas. More than 400 million people are infected annually and over 50% of the world's population is now at risk of infection due to living in a DENV endemic area [3]. The spectrum of disease manifestations is broad, ranging from asymptomatic or mild infection, through varying degrees of thrombocytopenia and vascular leakage

that is typical of dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF), to a severe shock syndrome and multi-organ failure [4].

Interestingly, in many endemic countries in Asia where DENVs are endemic, there have been cyclic repetitions of major DENV epidemics every 3-5 year [5]. During the last decade the severity, magnitude and distribution of dengue outbreaks have been appallingly high in the Indian subcontinent countries such as India [6], Bangladesh [7] and Pakistan [8].

DENVs are members of the family: Flaviviridae and genus: Flavivirus and have four serotypes; DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3 and DENV-4. In humans, disease severity varies between primary and secondary DENV infections and perhaps also between different dengue virus serotypes [9]. The viral lineage is continually changing due to the occurrence of rapid mutations resulting in the emergence of new variants [10]. The geographical distribution of DENV serotypes is very important because of the different evolutionary pressures in these different environments which are reflected in their different disease phenotypes.

Pakistan has experienced a number of dengue fever (DF) outbreaks since 1992 in 3-5 year cycles. The first confirmed dengue outbreak occurred in the southern Pakistan city of Karachi in 1994 [11].

Two DENV serotypes, DENV-1 and DENV-2, were identified during this 1994 outbreak [12], while DENV-3 was first reported in Karachi during the 2005–2006 outbreak [13]. During the outbreaks in Lahore from 2007–2009, DENV-2 and DENV-3 were reported as the predominant serotypes [14]. Dengue showed revitalization in 2010, especially in Punjab, Sindh and some cities in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa regions after massive floods occurred during the same year, while in the 2011 outbreak, DENV-2 and DENV-3 were the most prevalent serotypes but also with a lower incidence of DENV-4 [15].

DENV infections have recently risen again in all parts of the country, including some areas where DENV infections had not been a problem previously such as some regions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and Baluchistan. So far 6,000 suspected cases of DENV infections have been reported from Punjab [16]. In Sindh, the numbers of confirmed dengue cases has reached 1,474 during 2013 [17], while 8,343 cases have been registered from the Swat, Shangla and Bisham districts with official and unofficial death tolls of 36 (District Health Office (DHO) of Swat) [18] and 57 respectively reported up to the 18th October 2013. The DENV mortality rates, due to severe dengue (dengue haemorrhagic fever (DHF) and dengue shock syndrome (DSS) with or without multi-organ failure) reported from different outbreaks in Pakistan, such as the 2006 epidemic (5.8%: 25/431) [19], was significantly higher than any other country in the region where death rates of 1–2% are reported [20]. While DHF/DSS usually occurs during secondary DENV infection [21], many patients died during apparent primary DENV infections in Swat when DENV infections were first reported in Swat during 2013 [22].

This study was performed to identify the DENV serotypes in patients from Swat during the on-going 2013 DENV outbreak.

Materials and Methods

Approval from ethical committee

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Institute of Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering Peshawar.

Sampling

A total of 414 samples were collected from clinically diagnosed dengue patients at Saidu Teaching Hospital (STH), Swat.

DENV NS1 glycoprotein and anti-DENV IgG and IgM screening

Sera isolated from all 414 clinically diagnosed dengue patients were screened for dengue virus specific antibodies (IgG and IgM) and the DENV NS1 glycoprotein using SD Dengue Duo strips (Standard Diagnostics, Korea).

RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis and DENV serotype determinations

IgG and/or IgM positive samples were then analyzed for active DENV infections and, if positive, the DENV serotypes were identified using a nested DENV serotype-specific RT-PCR as described [23]. For this study, the DENV RNA was extracted from the DENV

sero-positive patients' samples using the Favorgen Viral Nucleic Acid Extraction Kit (Favorgen® Biotech Corp) following the manufacturer's instructions. The extracted DENV RNA was then reverse transcribed into cDNA and then subjected to nested (two step) DENV serotype determinations as previously described [23], with slight modifications in the thermal and chemical methods used. The final PCR products were analyzed on a 3% pre-stained agarose gels using a UV transilluminator.

Results

Of the 414 patients' serum samples collected for this study, 88.40% (366/414) were found to be anti-DENV IgG and/or IgM positive (Figure 1). A total of 28.68% (105/366) patients were found to have active DENV infections using the reverse transcriptase chain-reaction (RT-PCR). Of these 105 RT-PCR positive samples, the majority (65.71%: 69/105) contained DENV-3 followed by DENV-2 (33.33%: 35/105). One sample contained both DENV-2 and DENV-3, while DENV-1 or DENV-4 was not identified in any of these samples.

Figure 1 The proportion of anti-DENV IgG and/or IgM positive and DENV RNA-positive patients' serum samples.

Figure 2 The DENV serotypes prevalent in patients' serum samples collected in the Swat, Shangla and Bisham districts.

Discussion

The geographical location of Pakistan, with hot and humid summers, favors the breeding of the Aedes species. Factors responsible for the increased dengue incidence includes the lack of

effective mosquito control in the areas where dengue is endemic [24], unprecedented global population growth and the associated unplanned and uncontrolled urbanization, increased air travel, which provides the ideal mechanism for the transport of DENV infected humans and mosquitoes between different population centers of the world [24,25].

In the 2005 Karachi outbreak 4,500 dengue cases were registered. Over 21,204 people were reportedly infected in the country in 2010 [26]. The 2010-11 DENV out-break resulted in 18,000 cases nationwide. In 2011, a major outbreak of dengue occurred in Lahore with 16,000 cases and 350 deaths [27]. Lahore (population 15 million) is the second largest city in Pakistan, is a commercial hub of Pakistan and is linked to all parts of the country through various communication and trading routes. Due to lack of any effective control strategy, DENV also spread from this city into other parts of the country. During the ongoing recent DENV outbreak in Swat, up to the 18th of October 2013, a total of 8,343 cases with 57 deaths have been reported [18]. The mortality rate Swat was therefore considerably lower than the 2020-2011 out-break in Lahore which may have been due to many people in Lahore already being infected with at least DENV serotype during experiencing several mini DENV out-breaks from 2005 to 2009. Since all the four DENV serotypes were reported during the 2011 outbreak [15]

The situation will only get worse in the years to come due to the myriads of available breeding sites for the principle DENV vector species, *Aedes aegypti*. Change in the climate due to rapid deforestation and other human activities along with the ability of *Ae. aegypti* to adapt in a range of temperatures [29] is going to pose a high level DENV threat in Swat.

All four serotypes of DENV have been reported in Pakistan during dengue outbreaks in the last decade. During the outbreak in Punjab, DENV2 and DENV3 were found to be the most prevalent serotypes [14,15]. We confirmed the predominance of the same two DENV serotypes in Swat which indicates that this particular DENV outbreak is likely to be a continuation of the 2011 major outbreak of dengue in Lahore, since there is a lot of trade activities between Swat and Lahore and there has also been increased travel of visitors from the Punjab to Swat [30].

Acknowledgement

The authors highly acknowledge the support of the Directorate of Science and Technology, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (DoST).

References

- Guzman MG, Kouri G (2002). Dengue: an update. *Lancet Infect Dis*, 2: 33-42
- Strode C, de Melo-Santos M, Magalhaes T, Araujo A, Ayres C (2012). Expression profile of genes during resistance reversal in a temephos selected strain of the dengue vector, *Aedes aegypti*. *PLoS One*, 7: e39439
- Bhatt S, Gething PW, Brady OJ, Messina JP, Farlow AW, et al. (2013). The global distribution and burden of dengue. *Nature*, 496: 504-507
- Halstead SB (2007). Dengue. *Lancet*, 370: 1644-1652
- Ferguson N, Anderson R, Gupta S (1999). The effect of antibody-dependent enhancement on the transmission dynamics and persistence of multiple-strain pathogens. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 96: 790-794
- Gupta B, Reddy BP (2013). Fight against dengue in India: progresses and challenges. *Parasitol Res*, 112: 1367-1378
- Raheel U, Faheem M, Riaz MN, Kanwal N, Javed F, et al. (2011). Dengue fever in the Indian Subcontinent: an overview. *J Infect Dev Ctries*, 5: 239-247
- Rasheed SB, Butlin RK, Boots M (2013). A review of dengue as an emerging disease in Pakistan. *Public Health*, 127: 11-17
- Vaughn DW, Green S, Kalayanarooj S, Innis BL, Nimmannitya S, et al. (2000). Dengue viremia titer, antibody response pattern, and virus serotype correlate with disease severity. *J Infect Dis*, 181: 2-9
- Pugachev KV, Guirakhoo F, Ocran SW, Mitchell F, Parsons M, et al. (2004). High fidelity of yellow fever virus RNA polymerase. *J Virol*, 78: 1032-1038
- Chan YC, Salahuddin NI, Khan J, Tan HC, Seah CL, et al. (1995). Dengue haemorrhagic fever outbreak in Karachi, Pakistan, 1994. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*, 89: 619-620
- Akram DS, Igarashi A, Takasu T (1998). Dengue virus infection among children with undifferentiated fever in Karachi. *Indian J Pediatr*, 65: 735-740
- Jamil B, Hasan R, Zafar A, Bewley K, Chamberlain J, et al. (2007). Dengue virus serotype 3, Karachi, Pakistan. *Emerg Infect Dis*, 13: 182-183
- Fatima Z, Idrees M, Bajwa MA, Tahir Z, Ullah O, et al. (2011). Serotype and genotype analysis of dengue virus by sequencing followed by phylogenetic analysis using samples from three mini outbreaks-2007-2009 in Pakistan. *BMC Microbiol*, 11: 200
- Koo C, Nasir A, Hapuarachchi HC, Lee KS, Hasan Z, et al. (2013). Evolution and heterogeneity of multiple serotypes of Dengue virus in Pakistan, 2006-2011. *Virol J*, 10: 275
- 24-more-tested-dengue-positive. *The Nation*, October 22, 2013: Available from URL: <http://www.nation.com.pk/pakistan-news-newspaper-daily-english-online/lahore/21-Oct-2013/>,
- dengue-on-rampage. *The Nation*, September 24, 2013: Available from URL: <http://www.nation.com.pk/pakistan-news-newspaper-daily-english-online/lahore/24-Sep-2013/>,
- more-deaths-dengue-virus-claims-another-life-in swat. *Express Tribune*: October 22, 2013: Available from URL: <http://tribune.com.pk/story/620498/more-deaths-dengue-virus-claims-another-life-in swat/>,
- Daily Times*, October 29, 2006: Available from URL: http://www.dailytimes.com.pk/default.asp?page=20061029\story_29-10-2006_pg7_25, pg7_25
- World Health Organization (WHO) Fact sheet N°117 2013. Available from URL: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs117/en/>,
- Guzman MG, Alvarez M, Halstead SB (2013). Secondary infection as a risk factor for dengue hemorrhagic fever/dengue shock syndrome: an historical perspective and role of antibody-dependent enhancement of infection. *Arch Virol*, 158: 1445-1459
- ReliefWeb: Pakistan: Dengue Outbreak - Oct 2013. Available at: <http://reliefweb.int/disaster/ep-2013-000136-pak>,
- Lanciotti RS, Calisher CH, Gubler DJ, Chang G-J, Vorndam AV (1992). Rapid detection and typing of dengue viruses from clinical samples by using reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction. *J Clin Microbiol*, 30:545-551
- Gubler DJ, Trent DW (1993). Emergence of epidemic dengue/dengue hemorrhagic fever as a public health problem in the Americas. *Infect Agents Dis*, 2: 383-393
- Gubler DJ (1996). Arboviruses as imported disease agents: the need for increased awareness. *Arch Virol Suppl*, 11: 21-32
- Khan E, Hasan R (2011). Dengue Infection in Asia; A Regional Concern. *J Postgrad Med Inst*, 26:01-06.
- Butt Q (2010). Dengue will continue to haunt Pakistan for many years Available from URL: <http://tribune.com.pk/story/304451/dengue-will-continue-to-haunt-pakistan-for-many-years/>,
- Anantapreecha S, Chanama S, A-nuegoonpipat A, Naemkhunthot S, Sa-Ngasang A, et al. (2005). Serological and virological features of dengue fever and dengue haemorrhagic fever in Thailand from 1999 to 2002. *Epidemiol Infect*, 133: 503-507
- Tun-Lin W, Burkot TR, Kay BH (2000). Effects of temperature and larval diet on development rates and survival of the dengue vector *Aedes aegypti* in north Queensland, Australia. *Med Vet Entomol*, 14: 31-37
- Wilder-Smith A, Gubler DJ (2008). Geographic expansion of dengue: the impact of international travel. *Med Clin North Am*, 92: 1377-1390